

Femtocell Technology

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Abstract

Femtocell is a small cellular base station, designed for use in residential or enterprise. Connects to the service provider's network via broadband. Femtocell is one type of Indoor network which provide the wireless access within the particular area. Femtocells ensure that carefully planned cellular networks which may connect a specially of the citizens to the Internet and with one another. In this paper femtocells has such network which maintains the specialty of the data transfer through the network will femtocells prove more trouble than they are worth, femtocells just an exciting but Minimum stage of network evolution that will be improved Wireless offloading, new backhaul regulations and/or pricing, or other unforeseen technological developments? This paper overviews the history of femtocells, demystifies their key aspects, and provides a preview of the next few years' acceleration towards small cell technology. This paper reports, we also position and introduce the articles that headline this special issue.

Keywords— Femtocell, Spectrum, Femto, Pico cell, Mobile, Microcell.

Introduction

Femtocell acquired the name because they are much smaller than the standard cellular towers. Each of Femtocells works with the major wireless telecommunications standard and connects users with cellular provider via broadband Internet links. Mobile cellular and also 3G networks normally acquire poor penetration and reception in certain areas, like indoors. This decreases the quality of voice and video communication and slows down high-speed services.

A femtocell is a small device that is used to improve wireless coverage over a small area, mostly indoor. It is a small cellular base station it also called a wireless access point and that connects to a broadband Internet connection and also broadcasts it into radio waves in its area of coverage. For mobile handsets can handle phone calls through the femtocell, with the broadband

Internet connection. femtoMention a division that is mathematically represented by 10 raised to the power of -15

1.1 Introduction to Femtocell cellular networks

A femtocell is a simple low-power low-cost base station which is installed at the user's side that provides local access to the network that is some cellular technology (2G, 3G, 4G). A femtocell has an IP backhaul connection with the main purpose of the network through the local broadband access the user already has common situations. It is proposed that in a small basis, users will start installing their own femtocells in their areas, offices, etc. ABI Research predicts 102 million FC users worldwide with over 32 million. It is important to note that this represents an estimate of 3 to 4 users as per femtocell. That not much bigger than the widely used wireless access points, these femtocells are designed with a target cost of about 200\$, so they can be offered by the majority, hence a wide deployment is possible.

Figure: Network architecture of a cellular deployment with femtocells

LITERATURE SURVEY

Following are the terminologies needed to be discussed referring to Femtocell Technology

1 Early Origins

Firstly in a metropolitan area, “small cells” term used to describe the cell size, where a macro cell that which cell split into a number of smaller cells with transmit power reduction, known as microcells, and having a radius of several hundred meters in its nature. Simultaneously, cellular repeaters or “boosters” were being investigated as an alternative to small base

stations. These re-radiating devices were intended to help improve the signal quality in poor coverage regions, while reducing costs by not requiring a wire line backhaul. However, their reuse of the licensed spectrum for backhaul limited the achievable throughput, and hence these repeaters were neither helpful to the system capacity nor simple to deploy. In the 1990s, a precursor to cellular Pico cells began to appear with cell sizes ranging from tens to about one hundred meters.

2 The Birth of Modern Femtocells

New thinking on the deployment cost aspects of small cell deployment and configuration of cellular systems began to address the operational. These techniques have been applied successfully to special Femtocells where cost issues are amplified within the special network. A femtocell is especially different than the traditional small cells in their autonomous and self-accuracy. Additionally, the backhaul interface back to the cellular network – which is IP-based and likely supports a lower rate and higher latency than the standard interface connecting macro and picocells – mandates the use of femtocell gateways and other new network infrastructure to appropriately route and serve the traffic to and from what will soon be millions of new base stations. Perhaps more important than the need to provide cellular coverage infill for residential use, the mobile data explosion discussed in the Section I has mandated the need for a new cellular architecture with at least an order of magnitude more capacity.

3 Modern Femtocell Research

There is a growing nature of research on femtocells, of which we briefly report some notable early results which were extended to self-optimization strategies and multiple antennas shortly afterward. On the presented side, early model included new mathematical models and analysis, specifically looking at the uplink interference problem in CDMA-based networks with closed access.

The special model and approach was conducted with downlink and with multiple antennas. Other early work suggested adaptive access control to mitigate the cross-tier interference problem, which was given further attention in investigated the reverse link capacity of femtocells, modeling inter-cell interference as increasing ability of the femtocell technology and the presented network accessibility. This work was extended in which developed new analytical techniques to improve the optimization for WCDMA femtocell systems. Several papers have also considered interference coordination in OFDMA based networks, including co-channel interference management.

Motivation

Interference in Femtocell deployments

This approach is followed throughout this project for the actual subcarrier allocation at each Microcell and Femtocell. The complexity of the interference problem increases domestically and new strategies have to be designed for the prosperous performance of technology under the systematic view. If encounters three extradegrees of complexity in the interference problem. Focusing on the Uplink, there is interference generated by the Microcell users in the nearby of a femtocell.

Fig: Femtocell and Microcell Interfacing

States that, in order to guarantee close to 100 percent coverage, elaborated further Interference strategies have to be applied. Fractional frequency reuse (FFR) is mentioned as a possible solution, but good synchronization is essential for its implementation, and as already mentioned, that is not always possible when dealing with femtocells

Implementation Steps

1. Mobile sensing Femtocell networks

In this section I proceed to propose some algorithms and strategies in which a network provider could take advantage of the large amount of “voluntary” sensors that can be used to

to synchronize Femtocell networks and to mitigate the interference in this kind of two-tier deployments.

Figure: Femtocell and Microcell sensing

2. Femtocell coverage control

A Femtocell has already mentioned that the user installed low-power low-range base station in the premises to provide wireless coverage to referenced areas. That provides the big issue to highlight those femtocells foremitting in licensed spectrum, so that it uses more strict protocol for that particular task to make sure that a given femtocell radiates only in a geographical area where the network provider owns the spectrum, which are equipped with a GPS receiver. As in this way the system guaranties that radiating user is in an authorized area.

It may be locking a GPS signal and rather challenging as located indoors, so this forces the user to place the femtocell next to a window, for example. And there it might still be challenging to acquire the signal. That proposes a simple algorithm that would mitigate this problem and very likely completely solve it.

3. Femtocell synchronization

For the Femtocell network and the access of network to note that synchronization provides a big issue expanding the service for particular user in the indoor area, which can be further applications to gathering the location and GPS signal from a specialized group of mobile sensors or smart phones in the vicinity of the femtocell. This allows a very accurate timing acquisition of the system's clock under which the whole network functions. Femtocells, despite being low-power access points in the user's premises, are still a small scale of a regular microcell base station, so they require very accurate synchronization.

4. Frequency allocation in OFDMA-based access networks

It may not be to maintain work done in subcarrier allocation for OFDMA-based femtocells networks, it is very important to note that most of the privacies assume that the spectrum is partitioned in two segments so macrocells and femtocell, which do not share any frequencies. That means overall possible subcarriers are to be used a portion of them is proposed for microcell users and especially the rest is assigned to femtocell users. In the spectrum division is optimized to maximize the Area Spectral Efficiency. The ratio between the numbers of subcarriers allocated for femtocell users and the total number of available subcarriers.

Spectrum splitting allocation strategies achieve good results and interference should be mitigated but one main drawback is arrived that they present very low spectral efficiency. From this work we provide a simple interference mitigation strategy which invokes a reuse of the spectrum access points.

Benefits

The femtocell technology provides the better coverage of network which mostly used in networking and makes them perfect of their scale. Femtocell has the higher capacity to organize the cellular network and handle the network. In the form of mobile communication the femtocells technology mostly work for such an environment for producing the lower transmission power and has to be good quality. For the actual handset type the network must be provide the prolong handset battery life. For the mobile user the Femtocell network provide the range anywhere for the mobile calling.

Conclusion

In this paper the introduction on femtocell cellular networks and Location-Based Mobile Sensing analyze the specialty of the network and the accessibility. Femtocells are on a road to nowhere Unsatisfactory coverage and the increasing number of high-data-rate application are two driving forces for femtocell development Femtocells have the potential to provide high quality network access to indoor users at low cost Improve coverage Provide huge capacity gain. In this paper it concluded that the service for the indoor user within the particular area and permission of the user to access the services from the service provider.

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